

Time and Stochasticity in Quantum Entropy

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In quantum mechanics, a symmetry between momentum p and position x enters through the Heisenberg uncertainty relationship: $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$ where Δ denotes square root of variance. This symmetry appears to be extended to entropy as one often sees (1,2) both position and momentum Shannon's entropies, i.e. $-\int \text{density}(x) \ln(\text{density}(x)) dx$ and $-\int \text{momentum density}(p) \ln(\text{momentum density}(p)) dp$. These follow from $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)$, the wavefunction is $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Even if one considers conditional probabilities $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$ there is also a kind of symmetry.

In classical statistical mechanics, however, there is no symmetry between p and x . Maxwell-Boltzmann equilibrium is based on momentum i.e. two body collisions which is the stochasticity in the problem. If there is a potential $V(x)$, it is not stochastic so p changes according to $p^2/2m + V(x) = E$. We have argued in a previous note (3) that in quantum mechanics, stochasticity is also based on momentum due to momentum collisions with $V(x) = \sum_k V(k)\exp(ikx)$ which is the stochastic driver. If this is the case, how does one break the apparent symmetry between p and x discussed above? First, $p = m dx/dt$ while $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ in classical physics and the same sense is carried to a certain degree into quantum mechanics, so p and x are not symmetric. Furthermore, we consider two different expansions of $P(p)$. The first is based on $W(x)$ and leads to a Shannon's entropy of: constant + $\int dx -\text{density}(x) \ln(\text{density}(x))$. The second is based on $a(p)$ and leads to: constant + $\int dp -a(p)a(-p) \ln(a(p)a(-p))$. Which should be used? In a previous note (4), we argued that quantum Shannon's entropy follows from $P = a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ which is an addend in the equation for $W(x)W(x)$ (bound state). In this note, we try to use time to distinguish between the two Shannon's entropy possibilities and choose the one based on $a(p)$ which matches that from $W(x)W(x)$ i.e. $P = a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Boltzmann's transport theory is based on a physical phenomenon, scattering, and entropy follows from it. It seems that in some statistical approaches based solely on probabilities, there is a sense that physical processes do not govern the the problem. For example, Shannon's entropy is given by $\sum_i -P(i) \ln(P(i))$, so any probability seems to be a candidate. If $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ exist in quantum mechanics, one immediately has momentum and position entropy it seems. $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$ are not usually considered, otherwise they yield another two entropies.

We argue that in classical physics, equilibrium is created by two body scattering and so is related to momentum. In fact, in a number of notes, we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann (as well as Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein) distributions follow from scattering balance without any notion of entropy required. If one wishes to create an entropy, one may do so directly from the scattering equilibrium result, thus the two are directly linked.

Quantum Entropy Based on $W(x)W(x)$ for a Bound State

Quantum bound state spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ is often used as the probability in Shannon's entropy. We have argued, however, that:

$$W(x)W(x) = \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x) \quad ((1))$$

with $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ ((2)) is the probability to be used yielding:

$$\text{Shannon's entropy} = \int dx -2WxdW/dx - \int dp a(p)a(-p) \ln(a(p)a(-p)) \quad ((3))$$

The first term of ((3)) integrates to a constant regardless of W . ((2)) is not simply a mathematical term, it leads to density "humps" which are part of the physical observable $W(x)W(x)$. We argue that stochasticity is contained in ((2)) as it is the term which appears for each t_i measurement i.e. one momentum receives a stochastic hit and changes into another.

Quantum Entropy Based on $P(p)$

The expression for quantum entropy ((3)) follows from $P(x)$, but there exists also a $P(p)$ in quantum mechanics. How does it come into play? We give two expansions for $P(p)$.

$$P(p)=a(p)a(p)= \int dx_1 \int dx_2 W(x_1)\exp(-ipx_1) W(x_2)\exp(-ipx_2) \quad ((4))$$

And

$$P(p)=\int dx P(p/x)P(x) = \int dx a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x) W(x)W(x)$$

$$= \int dx \sum_{p_1} a(-p) \exp(-ipx) a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x) \quad ((5))$$

(We consider $a(p)=a(-p)$.)

((4)) leads to a Shannon's entropy of:

$$S= \int dx -WW \ln(WW) - \int dp 2pa(p) d/dp a(p) \quad ((6))$$

The second term of ((6)) integrates to a constant regardless of $a(p)$ if $a(p)$ vanishes a p being $p \rightarrow \pm \infty$.

The second leads again to ((3)). ((3)) and ((6)) are not the same, so the question is which should be chosen?

Time Considerations

The form $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ follows from $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. Even though time does not appear explicitly in either expression, it is implicitly present. $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ delivers a hit of momentum k , but this occurs at a particular time. A different momentum k_1 delivers its hit at another time. $P(p_1/x)$ occurs at one time and $P(p_2/x)$ at another. There is stochasticity in these results, but not complete randomness because: $[\sum_p p^2 / 2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E$. Using $a(p_1) \exp(ip_1x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2x)$ implies that at t_1 one has p_1 and at a tiny time later it changes to p_2 . A measurement is taken at a particular time which may have different outcomes, just like the toss of a coin or die.

Mathematically, one may write $P(x/p) = W(x) \exp(-ipx) / a(p)$ so that $\sum_p P(x/p) P(p) = P(x)$. Thus, at t_1 , a particle with momentum p may be at x_1 , at t_2 at x_2 etc. To apply $P(p)$ to Shannon's entropy, one must assume these x positions are stochastic i.e. one does not know which occurs (on average). This differs from classical physics and even hydrodynamics. For a plane wave with p , however, one may write $\exp(i(px - Et))$ which is not stochastic, even though it is a probability. Thus, the case of a fixed momentum does not seem to be like the toss of a coin or die or the hit of $V(k)$.

If one considers the actual motion of a quantum particle, it may be at x_1 at t_1 and have p_1 and then receive a stochastic hit and change to p_2 bringing the particle to x_2 at t_2 . In other words, there is a series of stochastic x and p 's. In such a case, it seems the idea of a constant p is mathematical. This mathematically constant p object may be said to have relative probabilities of $W(x) \exp(ipx)$, but these do not seem to occur at successive time values. For example, a particle might be at x_1 with p at t_1 , but at t_2 it will be at x_2 with p_2 . In such a case, one selects a subset of time events which correspond to momentum p . This subset has stochastic x values, but does not represent the full set of outcomes. It is not clear one may create a meaningful entropy by selecting only certain outcomes and ignoring others (for which momentum is not p).

As a result, we choose ((3)) instead of ((6)) for the expression of Shannon's entropy. It seems that simply using a probability to calculate Shannon's entropy may not be good enough, but that it should be related to stochastic outcomes for successive measurements taken at times t_i .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider two expansions of $P(p) = a(p) a(p)$, one based on $W(x) W(x)$ and the other on $a(p) a(p)$. Each leads to a different expression of Shannon's entropy and so one must choose between the two. We argue one may use time together with stochastic outcomes to try to choose. For $W(x) W(x) = \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1) \exp(ip_1x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2x)$ the addends represent a stochastic change from p_1 to p_2 at time t , just like the toss of a coin or die. For $P(p)$ it seems one needs to have a stochastic outcome for the question: Where is a particle with p at time t ? We don't think this is stochastic in the sense that a particle with p has a probability represented by $\exp(i(px - Et))$ which is the form of a wave and completely predictable at each given t . Furthermore, the actual particle changes from p_1 at x_1, t_1 to p_2 at x_2, t_2 etc so $P(p)$ pulls only a

subset of the data (data for which momentum is p). In such a case, there will be different x values with different, but these do not represent successive measurements.

Thus, we do not choose the entropy $\int dx -\text{density}(x)\ln(\text{density}(x))$ which follows from writing $P(p)$ in terms of $W(x)$.

References

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